

A Satirical Critique of Patriarchal Family Structure in Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things*

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Abstract:

Patriarchal family structure deeply embedded in Indian society in which men hold supreme power. Men use their power to dominate women and other genders by holding dominating roles in political leadership, social privilege and control of property. Arundhati Roy's The God of Small Things delineates a powerful critique of patriarchal family structure deeply rooted in Indian society. Roy employs irony, dark humour and subtle satire to expose oppressive power relations within the Ipe family in Ayemenem, Kerala. The novel depicts how patriarchal authority in India exploits and marginalizes women, prevents their rights and leaves them in utter disillusionment. Protagonist of the novel Ammu, being a woman, she is denied all rights which her brother freely enjoys. Like Ammu, Baby Kochamma, Mammachi also suffer due to injustice inflicted upon them. The novel delineates how rigid social norms perpetuate women subordination, marginalization and injustice across generation. Women are subject to violence, injustice and exploitation. Due to rigid moral codes, women in Indian society have been suffered, their position in family and society has been undermined. The novel presents the emotional and social consequences of male dominance. The present research paper is an attempt to explore how satire functions as a narrative strategy to critique patriarchal family structures and to unveil hypocrisy of social traditions. The examination of familial relationship and patriarchal dominance in this paper raises reader's awareness and it demands man woman equality in order to foster harmonious relationship.

Keywords: *Patriarchy, Satire, Family Structures, Marginalization, Subordination, Familial Conflicts, Male Dominance, Rigid Social System etc.*

Introduction:

The God of Small Things socially most acclaimed, 1997 debut novel is written by Indian English author Arundhati Roy. The book was awarded Booker Prize in 1997. The novel presents series of events against the backdrop of social discrimination and political upheaval in 1960s Kerala. Though casteism, misogyny, chauvinism, social boundaries and British colonialism are central themes of *The God of Small Things*, it also incorporates family structures embedded in patriarchy and social injustice. The novel depicts these issues to invite

introspection and positive solution. But still these are prevalent in the society which hampers social development and good family bonds. Patriarchy, dominant authority are responsible for familial deterioration.

The God of Small Things depicts deeply entrenched patriarchal society within the Ipe family, where especially Pappachi and Chacko use absolute power to dominate women. They are abusive, even Pappachi beats his wife Mammachi. The novel throws light on how patriarchy plays key role in demolishing family structures and at the same time it interrogates

power structures and demands introspection. The novel portrays very complicated relationship between the members of Ipe family in Ayemenem, India.

Research Methodology:

The present research employs a qualitative and analytical methodology to examine the satirical critique of patriarchal family structures in *The God of Small Things*. The primary source of the study is the novel *The God of Small Things* (1997) by Arundhati Roy. For primary sources the text will be analyzed to find out satire, patriarchal domination and family conflict. For secondary sources, critical essays and scholarly articles on the novel will be used as well as books and research papers on patriarchy and satire will be referred.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study and examine the depiction of patriarchal family structures in the novel and how they influence relationships within the family.
2. To explore satirical elements in the novel to criticize rigid social structure, authority and gender discrimination within the family.
3. To find out psychological impact of patriarchal oppression on Estha and Rahel.
4. To investigate hypocrisy and contradictions within traditional family values and social norms through satire.

Subject Matter:

1. Satire as a Genre of Literature:

Satire is a distinct genre of literature, not only used in literature but it is an integral part of art, paintings, cartoon, movies, internet memes, commentary, television shows, plays etc. It always aims reformation and in attaining it, it employs irony, ridicule, burlesque, humour, exaggeration to expose and ridicule human vices,

follies, abuses or shortcomings. It has been its ultimate aim is to provoke thought, highlight societal issues and inspire change. It invites readers' introspection and interrogates power structures. Great British satirist Jonathan Swift, Irish author is well known for his biting satire on British government. Writing during the time of immense poverty, famine and exploitative British policies, Jonathan Swift penned an essay "A Modest Proposal for preventing the Children OF Poor People from being a burthen to Their Parents or Country, AND for making them Beneficial to the Publick" (1729). The essay satirically details a preposterous way in which the Irish can solve poverty problem and its effects like begging women and children on the street. In Indian English literature, R. K. Narayan, Khushwant Singh, Shashi Tharoor, Salman Rushdie, Kiran Nagarkar, Eunice De Souza, Arun Kolatkar, Jug Suraiya, Aditya Magal etc. are key figures in satirical writing. They depicted societal disparities through their works. Among these literary luminaries, Arundhati Roy plays vital role in unveiling very absurd and threatening power structures which hamper social and family milieu.

2. Patriarchy:

Sylvia Walby is a sociologist and social scientist known for her work in social and complexity theory, gender regimes and patriarchy, violence and society including domestic violence and human trafficking. In her book *Theorizing Patriarchy* (1990) she talks about how patriarchy as dominant social structures is responsible for women exploitation and subjugation. She has composed six overlapping structures that define patriarchy. These structures state condition of women in different context. Patriarchy has come under attack by different sociologists, explaining patriarchy has been evolved due to historical rather than biological conditions.

Simone de Beauvoir, French existentialist philosopher in her most acclaimed feminist work *The Second Sex* (1949) has extensively analyzed and critiqued patriarchy. In *The Second Sex* she argued that how women have been subject to oppression and patriarchal societies systematically define them as “Other” inferior to men. How so-called men dominated society considers women as marginalized section of society and to suppress under dominance. Patriarchal power structures undermine the position of women in the society and family itself. Women are considered as helpless and dependent and thus subject to humiliation and oppression.

3. Satirical Exploration of Patriarchal Family Structure:

The Ipe family in *The God of Small Things* is an embodiment of patriarchal household. Male authority dominates domestic and social life. The legacy of patriarchy is carried forward to next generation, firstly by senior member of family Pappachi regulates dominance in the Ipe household, whose violent behaviour towards his wife Mammachi reflects the normalized oppression of women in traditional families. Mammachi, helpless and dependent remains silent due to social expectations and family honour. In such kind of family structures, we find hierarchal power relations where women always have to suffer and remain silent. After Pappachi’s death this legacy is carried by other family figure that is Chacko. He dominates Ammu and warns her that she has no place in the home as she is divorcee and has two children, has no right to live her life on her own accord.

The Ipe family is basically respected Syrian Christian family in Ayemmenem. The family disintegrates due to internal conflicts and contradictions of its family members. The family structure depicted in the novel is driven by rigid caste system, patriarchal hypocrisy, and lack of love, results in destruction of family structure.

Roy shows that patriarchal values are internalized both by men and women. Due Mammachi and Baby Kochamma’s belief and support to social norms, Ammu suffers a lot. This indicated how patriarchy is deeply rooted in family institutions and cultural traditions.

4. Hypocrisy of Baby Kochamma:

Baby Kochamma’s jealousy and obsession with family reputation intensify the conflicts within the household. Her hostility toward Ammu and Velutha leads to familial disintegration. She falsely instigates Estha to insult Velutha which places burden on Estha.

5. Sophie Mol’s Death and the Family’s Reaction:

Sophie Mol comes to Ayemenem with her mother Margaret Kochamma. The accidental drowning of Sophie Mol becomes the turning point of the novel. Instead of supporting the twins during this traumatic situation, family blames them. The pressure placed on Estha to testify against Velutha creates lifelong guilt and trauma.

6. Repression of Ammu in Patriarchal Household:

Ammu, a divorcee, creates tension within the family. She faces humiliation and tragic consequences due to patriarchal family system. She is denied social respect and is marginalized by her own family. She is treated as burden on family and denied her consent or authority in family matter. On the contrary, her foreign returned divorced brother Chacko is welcomed and had privilege to enjoy freedom. Roy employs irony to highlight gender biases. Ammu’s relation with the outcaste Velutha is considered as crime, a big blot on family’s honour whereas Chacko can have many affairs. Roy here employs irony to point out hypocrisy in Indian family system where men can have extra marital affairs where as women are stigmatized as immoral.

Ammu's forbidden relationship with Velutha is considered immoral. It challenges caste hierarchy and patriarchal morality. Ammu's relationship with Velutha becomes symbolic rebellion against rigid system imposed by society. But this rebellion against societal norms leads to Ammu's exclusion from society. When Ammu was locked, Chacko her brother threatens her to leave his house. He warns her, 'Get out of my house before I break every bone in your body!' (Roy, 1997: 225) This shows destructive consequences of rigid patriarchal power on family life.

In the context of marriage, marriage of Pappachi and Mammachi, Ammu and Baba or Chacko and Margaret Kochamma break due internal family conflicts. Pappachi used to beat Mammachi, Ammu also gets divorce from her husband and Mammachi never considered Margaret as her daughter – in – law, the consequence of it is failure in married life. Mammachi's opinion about her daughter – in – law was not good. Roy has depicted Mammachi's resentment for daughter – in – law as "Of course Mammachi would have despised Margaret Kochamma even if she had been an heir to the throne of England. It wasn't her just working-class background Mammachi resented. She hated Margaret Kochamma for being Chacko's wife. She hated her for leaving him but would have hated her even more had she stayed" (Roy, 1997: 168).

Ammu, a divorcee is not welcomed in her family. She and her children considered as burden. She asked to Chacko, 'Must we behave like some damn godforsaken tribe that's just been divorced?' (Roy, 1997: 180) Ammu's relation with Velutha, an untouchable is not accepted whereas Chacko is supported by his mother in the name of "Man's Needs." (Roy, 1997: 168) Mammachi made special provision for Chacko. She built separate entrance for Chacko's room so

that nobody can notice Chacko's relation with the women in the factory. Mammachi would secretly give them money. Roy has satirized such inclination of women who support men even though he is wrong and this leads to patriarchal dominance and this ultimately leads women subjugation and suppression.

7. Familial Conflicts Affected Young Minds:

The novel delineates shattered world of seven-year-old twins Estha and Rahel who are trapped between rigid social taboos, parental abandonment and the vindictive, conservative actions of their aunt, Baby Kochamma. Their mother, Ammu, treated as an outcaste for her divorce and forbidden interracial love. She is treated as inferior and dependent on her brother Chacko. And because of this Ammu and her children receive little respect and security in their family. The twins grow up witnessing humiliation and helplessness, which creates insecurity and instability in their own lives. They face cruelty, negligence, and deep emotional isolation and humiliation. They are treated as shameful burden and outsiders in their own family. Ammu being helpless, demands her children, 'Promise me you'll always love each other,' (Roy, 1997: 225). Due to familial insecurity and cruelty, Ammu is conscious about her children's safety.

Due to their mother's desperate situation, and family's hostility, children face harsh realities of life. The conflict leads to their forced separation, Eastha being sent to their father, destroying their childhood and leaving everlasting scars on their mind. The novel explores how rigid social norms, patriarchal power and familial conflicts lead to psychological deterioration of Estha and Rahel. Roy has satirized this very tendency of society in which to maintain fake honour and respect of family, such rigid traditions are followed and because of this helpless and marginalized sections of society get destroyed.

8. Family Conflicts and the Collapse of Patriarchal Authority:

The novel incorporates series of tragic events which lead to the collapse of patriarchal authority. The novel reveals the destructive consequences of rigid patriarchal values through Velutha's death, Ammu's exile, and psychological trauma of Estha and Rahel. In order to preserve honour and status of family, Ammu's interracial relation with Velutha is denied. The novel depicts the family not as a nurturing institution but as a site of repression and emotional violence. Ipe family's attempt to preserve fake honour and respectability, leads to destruction of healthy relationships and family bonds and replaces them with suspicion, resentment and control.

Conclusion:

The God of Small Things is powerful depiction of satirical critique of patriarchal family structures in Indian society. These rigid power structures are responsible for familial conflicts and often lead to the destruction of helpless. Arundhati Roy has harshly satirized through the experiences of Ammu, Rahel, Estha and Velutha. Roy's use of satire highlights hypocrisy, negligence, cruelty, humiliation and moral contradictions within patriarchal families. By revealing the tragic consequences of rigid social system, the novel challenges the traditional ideas of family honour and social hierarchy. In short Roy has subtly pointed out that patriarchy is a

destructive force which undermines both individual freedom as well as harmony in the family.

References:

1. Roy, Arundhati. *The God of Small Things*. India: Penguin Books, 2000. Print.
2. Prasad, Murari. ed. Arundhati Roy: Critical Perspectives. Delhi: Pencraft International, 2006. Print
3. Ranjith, Reena. and Dr. K.T. Manjula. "The Human – Nature Relationship in Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things*." *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, Vol – 9, Issue – 4; Jul – Aug, 2024.
4. Tashneem, Tahira. "Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things*: A Dalit Fiction?" *New Academia*, Vol. III Issue I, Jan. 2014. ISSN 2267 – 3967.
5. Cheriyan, Aswathy. "Patriarchal Domination in Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things* and Alice Walker's *The Colour Purple*." *Research Journal of English Language and Literature*, Vol. 5, Issue 1. Jan – March 2017. ISSN 2395 – 2636 (Print): 2321 – 3108 (online)
6. Rajiwale, Sharad, ed. *The God of Small Things (A Critical Study)*. New Delhi: Rama Brothers, 2001.
7. <https://www.litcharts.com>
8. <https://vidyaprabodhnicolledge.edu.in>
9. <https://www.britinica.com>